

CROSS-BUYING BEHAVIOR MODEL FOR CUSTOMERS IN LARGE CHAIN STORES

MODELO DE COMPORTAMIENTO TRANSVERSAL PARA CLIENTES EN ALMACENES DE CADENAS GRANDES

RESUMEN

El propósito de este estudio es proporcionar un modelo para el comportamiento de compra de los clientes en grandes cadenas de tiendas. En esta investigación, se utilizó el método de muestreo de bola de nieve y se entrevistó a nueve expertos en este proceso. El resultado mostró que la realización de la categoría fundamental en el contexto de las condiciones causales, ambientales y de contexto, se refiere a estrategias específicas. En esta investigación, y considerando los objetivos y las categorías identificadas, las categorías de "comportamiento de compra mixto" y "lealtad del cliente" se consideraron como categorías consecuentes.

Palabras clave: Comportamiento de compra, Comportamiento de compra cruzada, Tiendas de la fundación.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to provide a model for customer shopping behavior in large chain stores. In this research, the snowball sampling method was used and nine experts were interviewed in this process. Result showed that the realization of the pivotal category in the context of the causal, environmental, and context conditions, it refers to specific strategies. In this research, and considering the goals and categories identified, the categories of "mixed purchasing behavior" and "customer loyalty" were considered as consequential categories.

Keyword: Shopping behavior, Cross-buying behavior, Foundation stores.

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INTRODUCTION

One common aspect among all of us, regardless of the level of education, policies or commitments, is that we are all consumers of goods and services. That is, we use or consume food, clothing, housing, transportation, education, home appliances, vacations, services, and ideas based on a special order. As consumers, we play a fundamental role in the health of the economy (national and transnational).

The decisions we make about the demand for raw materials, transportation, production, services, etc., affect the success of some industries and defeat others. Therefore, consumer behavior is a comprehensive factor in the recession or in the current course of all business activities of the community. Hence, one of the main missions of marketing science is understanding and even guiding consumer behavior (Nasaie, 2015)

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the important issues in the investigation and recognition of consumer behavior is the purchase decision process. Most organizations that deal with consumer purchasing behaviors try to get information about what consumers are buying, as well as the cause, number, type, and location of their purchases. Unlike the type, number and place of purchase, it is not easy to find information about the causes of consumer or buyer behavior, since there is a consumer or buyer's response to this question (Salar and Rahmani, 2015).

In general, the purchase of the activity that the consumer is doing with his enthusiasm and the value of experiencing the decision-making process and its effect on the consumer is available. Buying is a way to get the goods or services you need. On the other hand, the process or decision-making process of consumers in purchasing is becoming a complex phenomenon (Danny and Dassar, 2016). Individuals display certain behaviors when they buy, and their identification and review can be effective in attracting customers and selling products in the future (Shafizadeh, Seyyedi & Ghasemi Dostashagi, 2019)

The relatively new concept that is nowadays in the field of consumer behavior is the intention to buy a combination or to buy goods along with other products. A hybrid purchase refers to the total number of product / service categories purchased by a customer since the time of the first purchase ever (Tung & Carlson, 2015). Sales are in fact sales of services or products to customers who are currently using their services. Selling other products and services to customers

reduces the cost of attracting customers and providing a competitive advantage over competitors.

Despite compound sales, increasing customer longevity and value, past research has pointed out that encouraging customers to purchase a combination of services and products is not a simple provider. The question of why customers decide to buy a mix of products and services and increase their relationship with a provider is slightly studied in the literature (Golrokh and Khanlari, 2014). Studies show that due to the growing competition in the retail industry (and especially among the chain stores) and the emergence of new rivals in succession, the profitability of such stores is in serious danger.

By the same token, if large chain-store to the decision of customers to buy hybrid understood and its dimensions are met, can adopt policies and appropriate measures and targeted, the benefits of buying a combination customer benefit. But in this area of theoretical vacuum, there is a lack of a native and comprehensive model of customer purchasing behavior in chain stores in the country. Therefore, the present research intends to answer the following question: "What model can be offered for customer shopping combination behavior in large chain stores"? Definition of Cross-buying: A hybrid purchase refers to the total number of product / service categories purchased by a customer since the time of the first purchase so far (Tung & Carlson, 2015).

- The main category (axis) is an idea, an incident or an event in which the concepts and categories are created on the axis;

- Ali circumstances: the set of conditions that triggers the phenomenon;

- Fields: Represents the special circumstances in which the phenomenon (main category) is located. The field also includes the features of the main category;

- Environmental conditions: a large structural field and external factors that can affect the main category;

- Strategies: A specific set of strategies or actions can be implemented in a context and under specific mediation conditions. In fact, strategies are actions that can turn the main issue into consequences;

- Consequences: The implications of the realization of a pivotal category in the context of the causal, environmental and context conditions, and through specific strategies (Stres & Corbin, 2018, p: 82)

In the following, practical research backgrounds are presented in two parts:

Ibrahim Pour Hasan Kalai and et al, (2017) conducted a research entitled "Investigating the Effect of Recommender Factors on Unfinished Purchase Behavior (Case Study: Chain Chain Stores in Mazandaran Province, Iran)". The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of recommendatory factors on unplanned purchasing behavior. Behzadnejad and Mansouri Moeid (2017) conducted a research entitled "The Impact of Managerial, Organizational, Marketing, and Service Quality on Purchasing Intention: The Role of Service Innovation (Case Study of Saipa Yadk Company)". The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of managerial, organizational, marketing and service quality on purchasing intention by examining the role of service innovation moderation in Saipa Yadak Company. A standard questionnaire was used to collect data and measure variables.

The statistical population included senior, middle and operational managers of Saipa Yadak Company. The results of this research showed that the dimensions of managerial capabilities of strategy dimension and entrepreneurship affects buying intent. From the dimensions of organizational capabilities, focus, internal communication, external communication, and organizational tasks affect purchasing intention. Both dimensions of marketing capabilities, namely, operational marketing and market orientation, affect buying intent. Service quality capabilities also affect the buying intent. Service innovation also affects the relationship between managerial capabilities and marketing capabilities on purchasing intentions. Innovation services do not affect the relationship between organizational capabilities and the relationship between service quality capabilities and intent to purchase.

Danny and Dassar (2016) conducted a research entitled "Measuring the consumer behavior behavior of chain stores based on media advertising, considering the mediating role of organization's reputation." The purpose of this study was to measure the customer behavior response of chain stores products based on media advertising, considering the mediator role of the organization's reputation. The statistical population of the study was food customers of reciprocal chain stores in the city of Tehran. According to the formulas of the sample size, 390 people were selected. In the first half of 2016, the opinions of these individuals were collected. Using standard questionnaire, the necessary information was collected and analyzed using appropriate tests in LaserLevel software. The results confirm the confirmation of all the assumptions under review. According to the results, it can be argued that customer behavioral responses to customers' desire to have the highest impact and characteristics of advertising on the behavioral responses of customers with the least effect among the hypotheses examined.

Tehrani and Safdari (2016) conducted a research entitled "Investigating the Relationship between Relationship Marketing Dimensions and Impact Purchasing Behavior of Customers in the Atkala Chain Stores in Golestan Province". The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between relationship marketing dimensions with impulsive purchasing behavior or non-scheduled customers in the chain of stores in Golestan province. The research method is descriptive-correlational research. The statistical population is all the customers of the chain stores in Golestan province. Due to the unlimited statistical population, the sample size is 384 people using Krejcie and Morgan table. The research method was simple random sampling and data gathering tool in this research was a questionnaire. SPSS software was used to analyze the data.

Vishal and et al, (2018), a research entitled "Will Rivals Affect Cross-buying Decisions?" They did. The research was carried out in the banking industry of India. The statistical population of this study was two groups of banking professionals and clients. In this research, the data were verified by a factor analysis method. The results of the research showed that competitors' prices, in comparison with the reputation and expertise of the main bank, have a greater impact on the intention to buy a hybrid.

Marcel and Raphael (2017) conducted a research entitled "Social bonding as a decisive factor in capital sharing and cross-buying behavior in b2b relationships." The study was conducted in Switzerland and in the light commercial automotive industry. The results of this study showed that the social bond between companies in the supply chain of light commercial vehicles industry has a significant effect on the hybrid purchasing behavior in b2b interactions. Krishnamurthy and Shainesh (2017) conducted a research entitled "Disregard for the old and the new hug: the effect of cross-buying behavior on the use of existing services." This research was conducted in the mobile operator's industry in India. The results of the study showed that the current customer purchasing behavior of new services would reduce their future use of existing services.

Heiner, Neeru, Florian and Katherine (2017) conducted a research entitled "Investigating the Factors Influencing the Hybrid Shopping in the Field of Environmental Services (Side)". The results of this study showed that price justice, paid commitment, and long-term relationships with customers could affect the buying behavior of the combination. Izhar and et al, (2016) conducted a research entitled "Investigating the Factors Affecting the Combined Consumer Shopping Behavior in Selangor Province". This research was conducted in Malaysia and on the customers of the food industry. The results of this study showed that product sets, orientation of convenience and well-being, price awareness, immediate

buying tendency, and perceived time pressure could affect the buying behavior of the combination.

Tung and Carlson (2015) conducted a study titled "The Factors Affecting Commodity Shopping Behavior in the Banking Industry". The results of this research prove the influence of some factors affecting the combination of customer purchasing behavior in the banking industry. Among other things, it can point to the impact of customer retention, which has a positive impact on its buying intention. Also, the results showed that customer convenience could also have a positive effect on the intention to buy a hybrid. Additionally, the positive impact of variables such as customer trust, customer satisfaction and commitment on the intention to purchase a combination of it was also confirmed. It should be noted that the results show that image conflict also has a negative effect on customer purchasing intention.

Lin (2016) conducted a research entitled "Customer-Oriented Composition :

Interactive Effects of Reliable Sales and Communication Quality". The results of this research showed that customers can ultimately have a positive impact on customer purchasing behavior. But this effect is not done without mediation. Rather, in the direction of the impact of customers on the behavior of the combination, the two variables of the seller's relationship behavior, and the quality of the relationship, also play a role of mediating variable.

Hong and Lee (2016) conducted a study titled "The determinants of buying hybrid in banking services in the culture of collectivism." The results of this research showed that the culture of collectivism can have positive effects on the trust and satisfaction of the customers; and this trust and satisfaction will have a positive effect on the intention to purchase the combination in the next stage. Hence, collectivist culture is influenced by the intention to buy a combination through two variables of mediation of satisfaction and trust. Irinja (2016) conducted a research entitled "Interactive shopping behavior stimuli among commercial customers." The research was carried out in Finland and among small and medium enterprises. The results of this study showed that loyalty, pricing, and customization programs could be effective on hybrid purchases.

Torsten and et al, (2016) conducted a study titled "Assessing and assessing the impact of oral-to-mouth marketing on hybrid shopping in the mobile market." This research was conducted in Germany and the United States. The results of this study showed that oral advertising could have a profound effect on combined shopping behavior in the mobile phone market. Werner and et al, (2015) conducted a study entitled "A Survey on Combined Shopping Shopping and Customer Loyalty". The results of this study showed that customer loyalty can directly

enhance the behavior of the buy-in, and, accordingly, the hybrid sales strategy should be based on loyalty programs.

METHODOLOGY

The present research is an exploratory survey in terms of its purpose and purpose. In this research, a group of marketing experts in the retail industry was considered as a statistical community and interviewed deeply.

In this research, snowball sampling method was used. In this way, the first expert was selected on the basis of the first review and, after completing the interview with the first person, he was asked to identify another person who could be in the field of customer shopping behavior in the chain stores and to help the richness of the research model. This process continued until the resonance of the researcher's saturation. Eventually, this was an interview with nine experts.

In this research, since the Foundation Data Theory Method was used, the main tools for collecting data were deep and unstructured interviews with experts. In these interviews, the researcher attempted, with a soft entry and early confidence-building of the interviewees, to ask questions in detail about the pros and cons of the combined behavior of customers in the chain stores, the environmental factors affecting it, the consequences of the phenomenon. ... And introduce the basic concepts for designing the model.

Table 1. Finalized concepts after analyzing interviews and removing duplicates in the open coding step

Concept	Code
Perhaps if the customer has less time to buy, they often make their purchases from a particular store	A ₁ , B ₄ , E ₆
Domestic chain stores must always benchmark their industry's best practices, both inside and outside the home	A ₂ , B ₉ , G ₅
You should also pay attention to the number of storefronts as it affects customers' selection of stores	A ₃ , B ₁ , F ₈ , I ₇
The store can create a variety of products that are economically and financially appropriate	A ₄ , F ₂
Shop staff can trigger customer purchasing behavior.	A ₅ , E ₄
The study and analysis of sales factors and the examination of the product variety contained in the invoices can further illustrate the purchasing behavior of the combination.	G ₁₀
The store can only expect hybrid shopping behavior when it comes to product diversity	A ₆ , C ₁₀ , I ₄
The correct layout and location of the chain store at the city level is very influential on the selection of the store by the customer for a variety of purchases.	B ₂ , D ₈
Sometimes the customer's goal is to buy, surf, and does not matter in the shortest time and from a single place	C ₁ , F ₉ , G ₄ , H ₄
Customers' habits of buying from a particular store or buying from different stores are effective on their combined buying behavior	A ₇ , D ₇ , G ₃

Source: Authors, 2019

Table 2. Finalized concepts after analyzing interviews and removing duplicates in the open coding step

Concept	Code
Exterior and environmental motivations can persuade a person to meet their needs from a particular store	A ₈ , C ₈
Some people in the family have learned that if you find a good store, try to always buy from there	B ₃
Shop staff should be aware that their behavior is influenced by the volume of purchases, the variety of purchases, and the repeated purchasing of customers	A ₉ , C ₁₁ , E ₁₀
Store brand strength can neutralize competitors' strategies	A ₁₀ , G ₂ , H ₉
Shop discount policies are a very powerful factor for encouraging customers to buy a hybrid	B ₅ , F ₄ , I ₆
Some customers believe that if they only buy from a store, they will remain anonymous	A ₁₁ , B ₆ , F ₆
Sometimes the customer is accustomed to having a small basket or general basket, which is also worth considering	A ₁₃ , C ₆ , E ₃
Some people consider buying as a disgusting process and they are fleeing	D ₁₁ , E ₂
Successful chain stores have come up with strategies and tactics in the field of hybrid purchases that studying and benchmarking them can reduce the testing and errors of domestic stores.	B ₇ , E ₁₃
The factors affecting purchasing can affect customer loyalty to the store.	D ₁ , F ₃ , H ₇
Some customers are diverse in choosing a place to buy	C ₃ , F ₁₀ , G ₈ , H ₁
Environmental advertising is one of the factors affecting customer buying behavior	A ₁₄ , D ₄
The brand can create loyalty in customers	B ₁₁ , D ₆
Shopping behavior and mother influence shopping behavior	F ₁
Performing various customer purchases from a store is a sign of his loyalty to the store	E ₁ , G ₉
You cannot force a customer to make all his purchases from a store and not go elsewhere	A ₁₂ , C ₉ , H ₃
Customer loyalty to the store is shaped by its interaction with products, prices, layout and staff	B ₈ , C ₂ , G ₇
The correct layout of the various parts of the chain store can reduce customer confusion and cause the customer to buy more useful time.	B ₁₀ , F ₁₁
Stores should not overlook the power of the impact of online social networks	F ₁₂ , H ₈
Some customers would like to know the features and conditions of other stores as well	C ₅ , D ₉ , I ₅
The brand's brand through trust building can convince the customer of a hybrid shopping behavior	C ₄ , H ₆
A hybrid shopping behavior requires a wide range of products in the store	A ₁₅ , C ₁₄ , E ₉
Sometimes the intrinsic desire of a person is to buy most of his supplies from a particular store	E ₈ , G ₁₁ , H ₂
The correct layout of the chain stores can help customers move smoothly and conveniently at the store and make them comfortable.	D ₂
Some customers are inherently self-employed in chain stores and try to fill their carts with different items.	A ₁₆ , C ₁₅ , G ₁ , I ₂
Some families oppose wider purchases from a specific location	B ₁₂ , D ₅ , F ₇ , H ₅
The economic conditions prevailing on society affect the volume and variety of people buying	B ₁₃ , E ₇
The range of product items that a person buys from a particular store during a month or year is a very important indicator	C ₇ , D ₁₀ , G ₁₂
Some customers consider the purchase process as enjoyable and spend a lot of time	C ₁₂ , E ₁₁ , F ₁₃
Some customers do not reject all available stores, they are not comfortable with prices and they believe in it.	C ₁₃ , E ₁₂ , I ₃
Group discounts (not volumes) can lead to cross-buying behavior	I ₁
The customer's free time to buy, affects his buying behavior	D ₃ , E ₅ , F ₅ , G ₆

Source: Authors, 2019

FINDINGS

OPEN CODING

This stage of analysis was dedicated to identifying and extracting the basic concepts of the content of the interviews. Accordingly, after conducting each interview, the investigator repeatedly extracted and coded the concepts in the interview text. A total of 9 interviews were carried out; 109 initial concepts were extracted; after examining and putting them together and eliminating repetitive concepts, 42 final concepts were identified, which are visible in

Table (1) and Table (2) (It should be noted that the codes beside the concepts include a Latin word and a number, the Latin word (in alphabetical order), the name of the person interviewed, and the number next to it, the number of the concept extracted from that particular interview).

Internal chain stores should always benchmark their industry's best practices, both internally and externally.

A2, B9, G5 You should also pay attention to the number of storefronts because it affects the selection of the store by customers.

A3, B1, F8, I7 The store can create a variety of products with good economic and financial conditions.

A4, F2 Shop staff can trigger customer purchasing behavior.

A5, E4 The study and analysis of sales factors and the examination of the variety of products contained in the invoices can show the combination of buying behavior.

G10 the store can only expect hybrid shopping behavior when it comes to product diversity.

A6, C10, I4 the correct layout and location of the chain store in the city is very influential on the selection of the store by the customer for a variety of purchases.

B2, D8 Sometimes the customer's goal is to buy, surf, and it does not matter in the shortest time and from a single place.

Buy C1, F9, G4, H4 Customers' habits of buying from a particular store or buying from different stores are effective on their combined buying behavior.

A7, D7, G3 Exterior and environmental motivations can persuade a person to meet their needs from a particular store.

A8, C8 Some people in the family have learned that if you find a good store, try to always buy from there B3 Shop staff should be aware that their behavior is influenced by purchasing volume, purchasing variation and customer purchasing repeatability.

A9, C11, E10 Store brand strengths can rival their competitors' strategies A10, G2, and H9 Shop discount policies are a very powerful factor for encouraging customers to buy a combination of B5, F4, I6.

Some customers believe that if they only buy from a store, they will remain anonymous from the market, such as A11, B6, F6 Sometimes the customer is accustomed to having a small basket or general basket, which is also noteworthy.

A13, C6, E3 Some people consider buying as a disgusting process and they are fugitives

D11, E2 the successful chain stores have come up with strategies and tactics in the field of hybrid purchases that studying and modeling them can reduce the testing and errors of domestic stores B7, E13 the factors affecting purchasing can affect customer loyalty to the store. D1, F3, H7 some customers are choosing a place to buy a variety of C3, F10, G8, H1 Peripheral advertising is one of the factors influencing customer buying behavior A14, D4 Store brand can create loyalty in customers. B11, D6 Shopping behavior and mother influence shopping behavior. F1 Performing various customer purchases from a store is an indication of his loyalty to the store. E1, G9 You cannot force a customer to make all his purchases from a store and not go elsewhere A12, C9, H3 Customer loyalty to the store is shaped by its interaction with products, prices, layout and staff. B8, C2, G7 The correct layout of the various parts of the chain store can reduce customer confusion and cause the customer to buy more useful time B10, F11 Stores should not overlook the power of the impact of online social networks.

F12, H8 some customers like to know about the features and conditions of other stores as well.

C5, D9, I5 Shop brand through trust building can convince the customer to have a hybrid shopping behavior.

E8, G11, H2 The correct layout of the chain stores can help customers move smoothly and conveniently in the shop and help them buy the D2.

DISCUSSION

In this section, each dimension of the paradigm model is discussed and the categories related to each one are introduced:

The main category (axis) is an idea, an incident or an event in which concepts and categories are created on its axis. In this research, and with regard to the goals and categories identified, the category "motivation for diverse purchases" was considered as the main and main category. That is, the core of the conceptual model is to focus on creating the motivation of various purchases by the customer.

Ali circumstances: the set of conditions that cause the appearance, amplification, or weakening of the phenomenon. Categories related to this dimension are defined as follows:

Customer's Attitude to Purchasing: This category refers to the kind of person's perception of the purchase that could make buying as a compulsive, annoying or loving one.

Client Interest in Urban Sightseeing: This category refers to the amount of interest or disgust of the person to go to the city and make purchases from different places.

Weekly free time: This refers to the amount of free time a person can spend during a week and the amount of time a person can spend in a week to complete his purchases.

Diversification in store selection: This category refers to the degree to which individuals choose to choose different stores for their diverse purchases.

Promotional (online and peripheral) stores: This category refers to the quality and quantity of chain store promotional activities to encourage customers to purchase hybrid purchases.

Composite discounts for commodity groups: This category refers to discount schemes for chain stores to encourage customers to perform hybrid purchases.

Store brand strength: This category refers to the value and strength of the brand chain stores in the minds of customers.

Customer purchasing habits: This category refers to customer specific habits (partial purchase, general purchases, purchases during the week or month, purchases from one or more stores, etc.).

Fields: Represents the specific circumstances in which the phenomenon (main category) is located and occurs in it. In this research, and according to the goals and categories identified, the categories "household buying culture" and "economic conditions of the society" were considered as the underlying categories. The culture of buying households refers to the buying habits of the family in which the individual was raised, and the economic conditions of the community, refers to the current economic situation of individuals as well as to enterprises active in the community (including chain stores).

Environmental conditions: a wide structural context and external factors that can affect the main categories and even the strategies. In this research, according to the goals and categories identified, the "modeling of the world's major chain stores" was considered as an environmental category. This means that chain stores operating in the country can model such stores in order to strengthen their cross-buying behavior.

Strategies: A specific set of strategies or actions is possible in a given context and with specific mediation conditions. In fact, strategies are actions that can turn the main issue into consequences. In this research, according to the identified objectives and categories, "product diversification", "proper store layout" and "empowerment of store staff" were considered as strategic categories. The variety of products refers to the wide range of product items provided by the chain store; in addition, the correct layout of the store refers to the interior design of the store and the degree of convenience for customers; and finally, the empowerment of the store staff, the training and development of store staff in It refers to better customer service and satisfaction.

Consequences: As a result of the realization of the pivotal category in the context of the causal, environmental, and context conditions, it refers to specific strategies. In this research, and considering the goals and categories identified, the categories of "mixed purchasing behavior" and "customer loyalty" were considered as consequential categories. That is, if the circumstances, contexts, main categories, environmental conditions and strategic conditions are well taken place, then it would be hoped that the cross-buying behavior and customer loyalty in the chain stores would increase. The next step was to insert the categories into a paradigmatic pattern that identified the conceptual model of the research.

CONCLUSION

Performing various customer purchases from a store is a sign of his loyalty to the store the amount of free customer's time to buy, affects his buying behavior. Perhaps if the customer has less time to buy, they often make their purchases from

a particular store Customers' habits of buying from a particular store or buying from different stores are effective on their combined buying behavior. Some customers are inherently self-employed in chain stores and try to fill their carts with different items.

Sometimes the intrinsic desire of a person is to buy most of his supplies from a particular store. Motivation for various purchases: Exterior and environmental motivations can persuade a person to meet their needs from a particular store the breadth of product items that a person buys from a particular store during a month or year is a very important indicator of the combined buying behavior. The study and analysis of sales factors and the examination of the product variety contained in the invoices can further illustrate the purchasing behavior of the combination. Some customers are choosing a place to buy diversity. A variety of choices are in store selection Some customers would like to know the features and conditions of other stores as well Some customers believe that if they only buy from a store, they will remain anonymous the store can only expect hybrid shopping behavior to provide product diversity.

A hybrid shopping behavior requires a wide range of products in the store Environmental advertising is one of the factors affecting the behavior of customers' purchases. Stores should not overlook the power of the impact of online social networks Purchasing behavior and mother influence shopping behavior. Shopping culture is household. Some families oppose wider purchases from a specific location Some people in the family have learned that if you find a good store, try to always buy from there Shop discount policies are a very powerful factor for encouraging customers to buy a combination of discounts for commodity groups. Group discounts (not volumes) can lead to cross-buying behavior Store employees should be aware that their behavior depends on the volume of purchases, the variety of purchases, and the repeated purchasing of customers. Empowerment of store staff: Shop staff can trigger customer-purchasing behavior. The economic conditions prevailing on society affect the volume and variety of purchasing of people. Economic conditions of society the store can create a variety of products that are economically and financially appropriate Store brand can create loyalty in customers.

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